

Integrated germplasm improvement—flood-prone

NDGR21: a new flood-tolerant promising line for eastern Uttar Pradesh, India

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About two-thirds of the rainfed lowland and deepwater rice area suffers from flooding during the monsoon season every year. Short-term submergence, or flash flooding, in flood-prone areas adversely affects initial rice establishment, resulting in poor yields. Submergence tolerance is therefore an important trait in rice grown in these areas.

The cultivation of Madhukar, a flood-tolerant traditional variety grown in rainfed lowland and deepwater areas, is narrowing due to its susceptibility to neck blast. NDGR21, a selection from Madhukar/Sena, is being developed as its substitute. NDGR21 produced stable yields in 1989-93 despite exposure to flood and drought periods at the early seedling stage in experiment station trials

Yield, maturity, and plant height of NDGR21 and check Madhukar.^a Uttar Pradesh, India. 1989-93

Variety	Ghaghrahat			Average yield (t/ha)	Farmer field trials mean yield (t/ha) 1989-93	Plant height (cm)	Maturity (d)
	Grain yield (t/ha)						
	1989	1992	1993				
NDGR21	2.1	1.7	3.0	2.3	2.5	135	141
Madhukar	1.7	0.8	1.8	1.4	1.5	155	149

^aCrops suffered from severe prolonged flooding during 1990 WS and from drought in 1991 WS at the early growth stages.

and in farmers' fields. NDGR21 yielded 1.7-3.0 t/ha during 1989-93 wet seasons compared with 0.8-1.8 t/ha for the check Madhukar. Average yield was 2.3 t/ha for NDGR21 and 1.4 t/ha for Madhukar (see table).

NDGR21 has a better survival percentage resulting from more panicles/m² and stable performance under intermittent flooding. NDGR21 has consistently shown a high submergence tolerance score in screening trials. It can survive for 7-10 d under complete submergence during the early stage and possesses moderate ability to elongate.

NDGR21 is weakly photoperiod-

sensitive and flowers in late October. It has resistance to stem borer, neck blast, and brown spot under field conditions. NDGR21 is erect, 125-145 cm tall, nonlodging, and matures in 125-150 d. Culm strength is intermediate. Lemma and palea are golden, grains are creamish white, and seed coat color is golden brown. It does not have awns. Panicles are intermediate. L-B ratio is 2.3 and test weight is 27.5 g.

Yield potential is up to 3.0 t/ha under flash flood conditions. This variety is being recommended for flood-prone areas of eastern Uttar Pradesh because of its consistent performance. ■

Crop and resource management

Fertilizer management—inorganic sources

Response to nitrogen in semidwarf scented rice varieties

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The demand for scented rice varieties for export is growing. To exploit the grain yield potential of recently released semidwarf scented rice varieties, it is necessary to determine their response to added N and their grain yield performance at moderate and high levels of applied N. These varieties are more responsive to N compared with traditional scented varieties, the N response of which is limited to 40-50 kg/ha.

We conducted a field experiment during 1990-92 wet seasons to study the influence of applying graded levels of N on grain yield potential and N response of selected rice varieties at the DRR's Ramchandrapuram Research Farm. Soil in the experimental plots was clay loam with CEC 45 meq/100 g soil, 0.1% total N (modified Kjeldahl method), 10 ppm of available P (Olsen's), and pH 8.2.

Three semidwarf scented rice varieties (Haryana Basmati 1, Pusa Basmati 1, and Kasturi) were compared with check variety (Basmati 370) at five graded levels of N: 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design, keeping varieties in main plots and N levels as subplot treatments with four replicates. A uniform dose of

22 kg P/kg as P₂O₅ and 33.2 kg K/ha as K₂O along with-half of the treatment dose of N were applied basally. The remaining N was applied in two equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 2-3 seedlings/hill. All other management practices were kept uniform.

The semidwarf scented varieties produced significantly higher grain yields than did Basmati 370 (see table). Grain yield of Haryana Basmati 1 was significantly higher than that of Pusa Basmati 1 and Kasturi but both these varieties were at par with each other during 1990 and 1991. The 3-yr mean indicated an increase in grain yield of 45.0% with Haryana Basmati 1, 41.0% with Pusa Basmati 1, and 45.0% with Kasturi compared with that of Basmati 370.

Grain yield response to N (kg grain/kg N) in semidwarf scented rice varieties. DRR, Hyderabad, India. 1990-92 WS.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)				N response (kg grain/kg N)				Nutrient response (kg grain/kg NPK)			
	1990	1991	1992	Mean	1990	1991	1992	Mean	1990	1991	1992	Mean
<i>Variety</i>												
Haryana Basmati 1	3.3	3.1	3.2	3.2								
Pusa Basmati 1	3.1	3.0	3.2	3.1								
Kasturi 3.0	3.0	3.0	3.5	3.2								
Basmati 370	2.4	1.9	2.4	2.2								
CD (0.05)	0.2	0.1	0.5	-								
<i>N level (kg N/ha)</i>												
0	1.9	1.9	2.3	2.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
30	2.8	2.7	2.7	2.7	29.7	24.7	14.0	22.8	7.4	6.3	3.6	5.7
60	3.1	3.0	3.2	3.1	21.0	18.3	16.0	18.4	8.4	7.3	6.4	7.4
90	3.5	3.1	4.0	3.5	17.7	13.8	18.9	16.8	8.8	6.9	9.4	8.4
120	3.3	3.0	3.3	3.2	11.8	9.4	8.8	10.0	6.6	5.3	5.0	5.6
CD (0.05)	0.2	0.1	0.3									

Incremental doses of N increased grain yield significantly up to 90 kg N/ha, after which it declined. The response to N during the second and third years was low because of stem borer damage, especially in high N treatments. Despite

these variations, the mean grain yield responses to N averaged over different varieties at 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha were 22.8, 18.4, 16.8, and 10.0 kg grain/kg N, respectively. The mean grain yield response to NPK at 30, 60, 90, and 120

kg N/ha irrespective of variety used averaged 5.7, 7.4, 8.4, and 5.6 kg grain/kg NPK, respectively.

The three semidwarf scented rice varieties recorded positive grain yield response to N up to 90 kg N/ha. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Effect of methods of *Sesbania aculeata* incorporation and nitrogen levels on lowland rice yield

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We studied the effect of different methods of in situ incorporation of green manure *S. aculeata* and three N levels on rice yields in two successive field trials, Sep 1992-Jan 1993 and Jun-Sep 1993. Rice cultivars used were ADT38 (13.5 d) and IR50 (10.5 d).

Soil of the experimental field in the first season was clay loam with pH 7.9,

EC 0.5 dS/m, 0.69% organic C, and 205 kg available N/ha, 8 kg available P/ha, and 411 kg available K/ha. Soil in the second season was clay loam with pH 7.8, EC 0.5 dS/m, 0.63% organic C, and 238 kg available N/ha, 7.3 kg available P/ha, and 37.5 kg available K/ha.

Different methods of in situ green manure incorporation at 45 d of growth were tested. Nitrogen contributed through green manure was 47.3 kg/ha in the first

Effects of methods of *S. aculeata* incorporation in situ and N levels on rice yield.^a 1992-93.

Treatment	Panicles/m ² (no.)		Filled grains/panicle (no.)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2	Season 1	Season 2
<i>Main plot</i>								
Incorporation method								
Sickle cutting + country plow	274	510	89.2	68.2	4.5	4.6	5.8	5.9
Animal-drawn Burmese setoon	246	516	85.3	68.6	4.2	4.6	5.4	6.0
Power tiller-operated cagewheel	264	555	88.4	70.4	5.44	5.1	5.7	6.6
Tractor-drawn cagewheel	305	561	90.4	70.8	5.2	5.3	6.7	7.0
LSD (0.05)	5	8	0.5	0.5	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2
<i>Subplot</i>								
(N level (kg/ha))								
0	249	509	84.6	64.9	3.5	3.9	4.6	5.1
50	275	541	88.3	70.2	4.8	5.0	6.1	6.4
100	293	557	92.0	73.5	5.5	5.9	7.0	7.6
LSD (0.05)	2	2	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2

^aInteractions were not significant.